

Thermal conductivity improvement of copper-carbon fiber composite by addition of an insulator: calcium hydroxide

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Abstract

The effects of adding calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) to a copper-carbon fiber (30%) composite (Cu-CF(30%)) were studied. After sintering at 700 °C, precipitates of calcium oxide (CaO) were included in the copper matrix. When less than 10% of Ca(OH)₂ was added, the thermal conductivity was similar to or higher than the reference composite Cu-CF(30%). A thermal conductivity of 322 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹ was measured for the Cu-Ca(OH)₂(3%)-CF(30%) composite. The effects of heat treatment (400 °C, 600 °C and 1000 °C during 24 hours) on the composite Cu-Ca(OH)₂(3%)-CF(30%) were studied. At the lower annealing temperature, CaO inside the matrix migrated to the interface of the copper matrix and the carbon fiber. At 1000 °C, the formation of the interphase calcium carbide (CaC₂) at the interface of the copper and carbon fibers was highlighted by TEM observations. Carbide formation at the interface led to a decrease in both thermal conductivity (around 270 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹) and the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE (10.1 10⁻⁶ K⁻¹)).

1 INTRODUCTION

Power density growth in integrated circuits (ICs) becomes faster every day. Thus, heat dissipation is critical; and, consequently, the cooling efficiency of the substrate must be improved. Heat-spreading materials for ICs must have both high thermal conductivity (TC) and low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) [1]. The high thermal conductivity prevents electronic components from overheating while the low CTE prevents mechanical failure after the heat cycle, between the ceramic substrate (with low CTE) and the heat sink [2].

Dissipating heat is one of the major problems occurring inside of power electronic devices. During the last 50 years, several studies have been conducted on this subject. Copper and aluminum are the elements most often studied because of their good thermal conductivity (i.e., 400 and 230 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹, respectively). However, their CTE is too high (i.e., 17 and 23 10⁻⁶ K⁻¹, respectively) compared to the other elements used in power electronic devices. In order to maintain the high thermal conductivity of the elements and decrease the CTE, the formation of composites reinforced with silicon carbide (SiC), carbon fiber (CF), carbon nanotubes, and diamond was proposed [3-7]. For example, using CF with copper can provide an inexpensive material that is easily machinable with good thermal conductivity (i.e., around 300 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹ with 30% vol. of CF) and a lower CTE (i.e., 12 10⁻⁶ K⁻¹ with 30% vol. of CF)

Moreover, the properties of a composite are linked to the properties of the matrix, the reinforcement, and the interphase. Consequently, improving the interphase is an important challenge. In a copper-carbon fiber (Cu-CF) composite, the copper and carbon are totally inert so the interface is only mechanical (i.e., connection with the porosity and the defects and the fretting induced by the difference between the CTE of the matrix and the reinforcement). After several thermal cycles, the interphase is degraded, leading to a decrease in the thermal conductivity and an increase in the CTE.

In order to improve the interface between copper and carbon, the use of carbide-former elements was proposed [6-10]. Carbide formation induces a chemical bond between a matrix and reinforcements leading to an improvement in the properties. For example, Schubert et al. [6] have shown an improvement by a factor of 2 in the thermal conductivity of a composite of chromium copper alloy 0.8

(CuCr_{0.8}) and diamond. Numerous carbide-former elements, such as boron, chromium, titanium, aluminum, and zirconium, have been studied. Three important points highlight the efficiency of a carbide-former element. First, the standard enthalpy of the carbide formation must be negative and around -60 to -20 kJ.mol⁻¹. Secondly, the carbide-former elements must have a low solubility with the matrix. Thirdly, the carbide layers formed during the sintering must be controlled and kept thin in order to maintain a maximum thermal interface conductance.

Based on these criteria, calcium, with an enthalpy formation of -62 kJ.mol⁻¹, appears to be a good candidate. In this paper, the effects of adding calcium into the Cu-CF(30% vol.) composite were studied. Because calcium is not stable under air (i.e., the rapid formation of calcium hydroxide), two solutions are proposed:

i) Using commercial Ca(OH)₂.

According to the literature, the formation of calcium carbide (CaC₂) from calcium hydroxide Ca(OH)₂ is possible. Ca(OH)₂ is decomposed into calcium oxide (CaO), above 550 °C, according to Reaction (1)[11]

Then, CaO reacts with carbon to form CaC₂, according to Reaction (2). This reaction starts around 1000 °C [12].

ii) Using a copper-calcium (CuCa) binary compound.

In this way, the calcium stays metallic and can be formed more easily (CaC₂). Moreover, the low melting point of a CuCa compound (i.e., 567 °C) could induce a semisolid sintering improving the diffusion of Ca and reducing the porosity [13].

In this paper, how adding Ca(OH)₂ affects the thermal conductivity and CTE of a Cu-CF(30% vol.) composite is discussed. Microstructure analyses were conducted in order to explain the effects on the thermal conductivity values of adding calcium (Ca). The effects of adding CuCa are not discussed in this paper.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Dendritic copper (Eckart Granules Poudmet, 30 μm), carbon fibers (l ≥ 100 μm, Φ = 5 μm), and calcium hydroxide powder (Aldrich, 1 μm) were used in the preparation of the Cu-Ca(OH)₂(X% vol.)-CF(30% vol.) composites. The carbon fibers are PAN fibers which exhibit a longitudinal thermal conductivity of 300 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹ and a perpendicular thermal conductivity of 10 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹.

Copper, carbon fiber, and Ca(OH)₂ were then mixed in the appropriate amounts using a 3D Turbula for 2 hours. Then the mixture was hot pressed in a steel mold (Φ = 40 mm) at 700 °C/80 MPa for 30 min. The pellets were then trepanned in order to obtain pellets 6 mm in diameter, with the carbon fibers oriented. The orientation of the fibers is due to the pressure applied during sintering. Carbon fibers are randomly dispersed in a plane, perpendicular to the axis pressure direction. In this study, the pressure direction was the reference for the orientation of the fibers.

The densities of the composites were measured using both the Archimedes and geometric methods and compared to the theoretical densities calculated using the rule of mixture:

$$\rho_c = \rho_m V_m + \rho_{CF} V_{CF} + \rho_x V_x$$

where, ρ_m, ρ_{CF}, and ρ_x are the densities of the copper matrix, the carbon fibers, and the calcium compounds, respectively, given in g.cm⁻³. V_m, V_{CF}, and V_x are the volume fractions of the copper matrix, the carbon fibers, and the calcium compounds, respectively.

All samples were characterized by X-ray powder diffraction using a Philips PW 1050 diffractometer with CuKα radiation (λ = 0.15405 nm). These patterns were scanned by steps of 0.02° (2θ) from 5° to 80° with a constant counting time of 30 s. The bulk samples were investigated by electron probe microanalyses (EPMA) with metallic Ca (K_α), Cu (K_α), and C (K_α) as standards.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs were acquired using a Tescan VEGA II-SBH working at 10 and 20 kV with a current beam of 90 μA. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) micrographs were done using a Joel 2100 microscope working at 200 kV and equipped with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS).

The thermal diffusivity D ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) was measured using a Flash laser technique (Netzsch LFA 457) on 6 mm diameter samples with a thickness between 2 and 5 mm. Thermal diffusivity was measured at 70 °C for reasons of measurement stability. Each measurement was performed at least 30 times, and an average value was calculated. The CTE was measured with a differential dilatometer (Netzsch DIL 402C). The heating rate was 2 °C/min and ranged from room temperature to 250 °C under argon atmosphere. The CTE value is an average of at least six cycles measured where only the linear part was used (i.e. between 80 °C and 200 °C).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Composite Cu-Ca(OH)₂ (X%)-CF(30%) After Sintering

Numerous composites with the composition Cu-Ca(OH)₂(X%)-CF(30%) were fabricated where $x = 0, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 10,$ and 30%. The relative density ($d_{\text{exp}}/d_{\text{theoric}}$) of each composite is given in Table 1. For each sample, the sintering conditions led to the required density, above 98%. However, when the content of Ca(OH)₂ increased, the density increased, up to 106%. These too-high values can be explained by the transformation of Ca(OH)₂ in CaO (Reaction 1) that can occur during the sintering. Indeed, if the density of CaO (i.e., 3300 $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$) were used instead of Ca(OH)₂ (i.e., 2240 $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$), the relative density would decrease at 100% (Table 1, Lines 2 and 4). Thus, the fact that Reaction 1 can occur during sintering at 700 °C was considered and was in agreement with the literature [11].

Ca(OH) ₂ content	0	0.5	1	3	5	10	30
Geometric density (%) considering Ca(OH)₂ density	98.9	98.3	99.4	101	101	102.7	106.8
Geometric density (%) considering CaO density	98.9	98.2	99.3	100.6	100.4	101.5	102.6
Archimedes density (%) considering Ca(OH)₂ density	100.4	99.8	100.6	100.2	101.4	101.6	105.4
Archimedes density (%) considering CaO density	100.4	99.8	100.5	99.8	100.8	100.5	101.2

Table 1: Archimedes and Geometric relative densities of samples Cu-Ca(OH)₂(X%)-CF(30%) ($W = 0, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 10, 30$) considering the density of Ca(OH)₂ (grey) and the density of CaO (white).

In Figure 1, the X-Ray patterns are given for $x = 0, 10,$ and 30% vol. The X-Ray pattern of the sample Cu-Ca(OH)₂(30%)-CF(30%) exhibited some new peaks, which can be indexed by CaO. Therefore, the transformation of Ca(OH)₂ into CaO (Reaction 1), during the process, was confirmed. Moreover, for each composition, the peaks of copper were fixed. There was no variation in the lattice parameters. Consequently, the calcium did not make a solid solution with the copper, which agreed with the binary diagram.

Figure 1: X-Ray patterns of Cu-CF(30%), Cu(OH)₂(10%)-CF(30%), and Cu(OH)₂(30%)-CF(30%) composites.

According to the SEM micrographs (back scattering electrons, Figure 2), the three elements can be easily detected. No porosity is visible at the mechanical interface between the copper and the carbon fibers. These observations are in good agreement with the relative density measured for each sample. The Ca(OH)_2 decomposed in CaO was mainly embedded in the copper matrix. The size of the CaO precipitates was around 10 to 15 micrometers. The size of the precipitates remains the same regardless of the amount of CaO , but their number increases when this amount increases. The precipitates near the carbon fibers seemed to interact with them (Figure 3). However, the nature of the interactions is unknown. Indeed, according to the literature, the formation of CaC_2 from CaO seems possible above 1000 °C. Thus, at a 700 °C sintering temperature, carbide should not be formed during the process. However, higher temperatures, inside the bulk material, can be locally generated due to the decomposition of Ca(OH)_2 .

Figure 2: SEM micrographs (Back Scattering Electrons) of the composites (a) Cu- Ca(OH)_2 (3%)-CF(30%), (b) Cu- Ca(OH)_2 (5%)-CF(30%), (c) Cu- Ca(OH)_2 (10%)-CF(30%).

The sample with 3% of CaO was investigated by TEM analysis. The micrographs and the electron diffraction pattern are given in Figure 4. The EDS analysis confirmed the presence of calcium (grey phase on the micrograph) at the interface between the copper and the carbon fiber. This interphase, where the calcium is located, seems granulous and composed of nanometric particles (Figure 4-b). This nanostructuration is probably induced by the decomposition of Ca(OH)_2 . Ghosh et al. reported similar behaviors [14]. They explain that, during sintering, one grain of Ca(OH)_2 was progressively decomposed in small particles of CaO from the edge to the core. The electron diffraction pattern (Figure 4-c) can be indexed using the crystallographic planes of copper, carbon, and calcium oxide. This observation confirms the transformation of $\text{Ca(OH)}_2/\text{CaO}$. No carbide was found in the numerous electron diffraction patterns studied.

Figure 3: SEM micrograph (BSE) of the composite Cu- Ca(OH)_2 (3%)-CF(30%).

The thermal conductivity properties and the CTE were measured for each sample. The results are given in Figure 5. The composite without Ca(OH)_2 , sintered with the same conditions as the composite with Ca(OH)_2 , exhibited a parallel thermal conductivity of $303 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, a perpendicular thermal conductivity of $202 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, and a parallel CTE of $11.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$. These values are slightly higher than the ones from the literature and will be used as reference values in this paper [15-17]. For the samples with a low content of Ca(OH)_2 (i.e., $\leq 1\%$), the parallel thermal conductivity did not change;

but the perpendicular thermal conductivity decreased about 5% for $x=1\%$ of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. For $x=3\%$, an improvement of around 7% of the parallel thermal conductivity was measured. In the same way, a higher or similar thermal conductivity was measured for $x=5\%$ and $x=10\%$. This improvement remains unexplained. Indeed, CaO material exhibited a low thermal conductivity value (i.e., $20 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$). The reasons why the thermal conductivity increased while a fraction of CaO increased are still unknown. The nanostructuring of CaO from the decomposition of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ could be one of the reasons. However, when the content of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ increased, the perpendicular thermal conductivity decreased. The CTE was almost the same for all of the composite materials. Thus, we can suppose that the addition of hydroxide plays no role in thermal expansion. A variation in the CTE can be directly correlated to a change of the interface [18]. Consequently, the calcium hydroxide (or calcium oxide) did not change the interface properties between the metallic matrix and the carbon fiber.

Figure 4: Micrographs (a,b) and the electron diffraction pattern (c) of the compound $\text{Cu-Ca}(\text{OH})_2(3\%)\text{-CF}(30\%)$, obtained by TEM analysis. The micrograph (b) is a zoom of the micrograph (a) (red rectangle).

To conclude, the addition of 3% of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ led to an improvement in the parallel thermal conductivity of 7% without affecting the interface between the matrix and fibers. We can suppose that chemical interactions at the interface could both decrease the CTE and maintain a good thermal conductivity. For these reasons, few heat treatments have been done on the composite $\text{Cu-Ca}(\text{OH})_2(3\%)\text{-CF}(30\%)$ in order to enhance the chemical interaction between the matrix and fibers through calcium carbide formation.

Figure 5: Thermal conductivities (circle and square) and coefficient of thermal expansion (triangle) of the composite Cu-Ca(OH)₂(X%)-CF(30%) (with X= 0, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 10, 30).

3-2 Effect of the Heat Treatment on the Cu-Ca(OH)₂(3%)-CF(30%) Composite

The Cu-Ca(OH)₂(3%)-CF(30%) composite was chosen to analyze the effect of different heat treatment temperatures on interfacial Cu/C and composite properties. The compound was heat treated for 24 hr. under nitrogen flux at 400 °C, 600 °C, and 1000 °C. No evolution of the composite density was analyzed after the heat treatments.

Each sample was studied by EPMA analysis. The maps of the repartition of the carbon, copper, and calcium elements are given in Figure 6. Before heat treatment, the composite was described as a copper matrix with precipitates of calcium inside. After the heat treatment at 400 °C, the size of the precipitates decreased, and the calcium seemed to be more distributed around the carbon fibers. Nevertheless, some precipitates with a size around 10 microns were still visible in the copper matrix. At 600 °C, the size of the calcium precipitates inside the copper matrix decreased. Moreover, more calcium was observed around the carbon fibers. At 1000 °C, the observations were the same. A higher calcium content was observed along the carbon fibers forming layers as well as precipitates with a size around 10 microns or less. The heat treatment increased the migration behavior of the calcium inside the matrix to the matrix-fiber interface. When the temperature increased, the concentration of calcium at the interface increased.

In order to study the interface/interphase and the interaction between calcium and carbon fibers, the sample heat treated at 1000 °C for 24 hr. was analyzed using TEM. Several regions of the Cu/C materials were analyzed (i.e., eight different geographic zones were observed); and representative micrographs and electron diffraction patterns are given in Figure 7. The calcium layer (Figure 7-a) between the copper and carbon fiber had a thickness of about 1 micrometer, and it was several micrometers long. CaC₂ phase, copper, and carbon fibers can index the electron diffraction patterns performed at the carbon fiber-calcium and copper-calcium interfaces and the center of the rich calcium zone. Thus, calcium-rich zones were transformed into CaC₂. In comparison to the sample after sintering, the CaO phase was replaced by the CaC₂ phase. At 1000 °C, a CaO phase reacts with carbon fiber to form a CaC₂ interphase. Wu et al. and Li et al. report, respectively, a minimum of 1000 °C and 1550 °C for the start of the reaction between CaO and C [12, 19]. Therefore, our results are in good accordance with the literature, albeit with a lower temperature of reaction. Moreover, the formation of CaC₂ was considered total, as calcium oxide was not observed around the carbon fibers or inside the copper matrix. The calcium rich zones embedded in the copper matrix could not be observed by TEM analysis; therefore, the composition of these precipitates after the heat treatment is unknown.

Figure 6: Mapping of calcium, carbon and copper elements inside the composite Cu-Ca(OH)₂(3%)-CF(30%) obtained by EPMA analysis.

Figure 7: Micrographs (a) and the electron diffraction pattern done on the selected zZones 1, 2, and 3 (b) of the compound Cu-Ca(OH)₂(3%)-CF(30%) after the heat treatment at 1000 °C during 24 hr, obtained by TEM analysis.

To summarize, the heat treatment led to a diffusion of calcium oxide at the interface; and then a reaction occurred between calcium oxide and carbon to form carbide. The first step began at 400 °C; and the second step was detected beginning at 1000 °C, which is at the lower end of the temperature range known for this reaction.

The thermal conductivity properties and the CTE were measured for each sample heat-treated. The results are given in Figure 8. From a thermal point of view, the heat treatments induced a decrease in thermal conductivity. For example, the parallel thermal conductivity decreased about 11% and 16% after the heat treatment at 400 °C and 600 °C (or 1000 °C), respectively. Thus, the calcium oxide diffusion at the interface acted as an obstacle to thermal conductivity. The precipitates of the calcium oxide inside the copper matrix, for the sample with 3% of Ca(OH)₂, improved thermal conductivity while the same calcium oxide in the interface matrix/fiber decreased it. This decrease could be explained by the localization of the calcium oxide. Indeed, the calcium oxide layers around the carbon fibers changes the interface/interphase properties. These insulator layers of about 1 micrometer limited the phonon and electron transfer between the copper and the carbon fibers (i.e., formation of a thermal resistance). Nevertheless, the decrease at 1000 °C was unexpected. The formation of carbide should have increased the thermal conductivity [6, 9-10]. However, the carbide layers formed during the sintering must be controlled (i.e., strong interface, thin interphase) in order to maintain a maximum thermal interface conductance. They showed that more than 1% wt. of carbide elements induced a

decrease in the thermal conductivity. The high content of Ca(OH)_2 in our sample (i.e., 3% vol.) and the thickness of the carbide layers ($\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$) could explain the decrease.

Figure 8: Thermal conductivities and coefficient of thermal expansion of the composite $\text{Cu-Ca(OH)}_2(3\%)\text{-CF}(30\%)$ after sintering and heat treatment at 400 °C, 600 °C and 1000 °C

From a thermomechanical point of view, an increase of about 1 unit of the CTE was measured after annealing at 400°C (i.e., $12.7 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$). Then, the CTE decreased until $10.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for the sample heat-treated at 1000 °C. These variations can be explained by the calcium diffusion and carbide formation. Indeed, for the composites after sintering, the precipitates of calcium oxide inside the copper matrix did not affect the CTE. At 400 °C and 600 °C, the diffusion of calcium oxide at the matrix/fiber interface led to the formation of calcium oxide layers. Consequently, the mechanical interface between the copper and the carbon fibers was replaced by a new interface (i.e., copper-calcium oxide-carbon fibers). Therefore, the formation of a brittle phase between copper and carbon fiber weakened the interface. The decrease in the CTE at 1000 °C can be explained by the formation of calcium carbide from calcium oxide. This reaction induced the formation of a chemical bond between the carbon fibers and the calcium. This phenomenon led to a stronger interface which limited the thermal expansion.

4 CONCLUSION

The effects of adding calcium inside a composite $\text{Cu-CF}(30\% \text{ vol.})$ were investigated. The goal was to form calcium carbide at the interface of copper and carbon fibers in order to improve the thermal properties and the CTE. Because calcium is highly sensitive to air, the calcium hydroxide was chosen as the element to be added. During sintering, the calcium hydroxide was converted into calcium oxide, located in the copper matrix. For 3% vol. of Ca(OH)_2 , a 7% improvement in the parallel thermal conductivity and a stable CTE were measured. Several heat treatments were then done on the sample with 3% vol. of Ca(OH)_2 . At 400 °C and 600 °C, the calcium oxide diffused from the copper matrix to the interface of the copper and carbon fibers. This led to the formation of a brittle and insulator phase at the interface, which led to a decrease in the thermal conductivity and an increase in the CTE. At 1000 °C, the calcium carbide formation occurred; and a decrease in the CTE was measured. Thus, we highlight the carbide formation from Ca(OH)_2 in the $\text{Cu-Ca(OH)}_2\text{-CF}$ composite using chemical reactions during sintering and heat treatment. Using the same method with a lower content of Ca(OH)_2 (i.e., 0 to 0.5% vol.), could lead to the improvement of the global thermal mechanical properties correlating with a decrease in the CTE.

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